

Building Brand Awareness and Brand Loyalty through Social Media Marketing and Brand Equity

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Abstract

The development of the times that occurred was also followed by changes in the food industry. Various trends and types of food from time to time change very quickly so that they are increasingly attractive and present many choices for consumers. Marketers must be careful and smart in responding to market opportunities, especially in the current 4.0 era. Developing marketing trends must be able to follow, as well as consumer trends due to the impact of market shifts. Companies must have unique values so that they are more competitive and attractive to consumers, which can be in the form of product variants, product brands, promotion strategies, prices and distribution systems. The phenomenon of marketing success through social media which has been increasingly widespread lately is evidence of the increasing importance of the existence of social media in marketing which makes it easier for consumers and pampered. The focus and target of marketing in the current digital era is to maintain consumer loyalty, which previously was assumed to only try to get as many new customers as possible. One strategy that can be used in an effort to gain consumer loyalty is to utilize social media. Customer loyalty to a product or service can be grown through a strategy to increase brand loyalty. This paper specifically discusses how to build brand awareness and brand loyalty through social media marketing and brand equity

Key words: Brand Awareness, Brand Loyalty, Social Media Marketing, Brand Equity

Introduction

Currently communication and interpersonal interaction have changed due to the influence of technological advances and the existence of internet access that allows individuals to be able to communicate without being limited by space and time. As a result of the development of technology and the internet, various means of internet-based public communication or what is commonly referred to as Social Media have emerged. Social media is an internet-based communication tool that was originally created just to communicate, but nowadays the functions of social media also vary. There are many positive and useful things that can be done through Social Media, such as spreading news to doing marketing. Currently, users of social media also continue to increase so that social media can also become one of the most promising modern marketing media. Modern marketing is also of course different from previous

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marketing which is more conventional. One of the modern marketing tools itself is Social Media where anyone who uses Social Media can see and know the promotions carried out by the company so that they can expand the range of promotions carried out by the company. Modern marketing using social media also of course makes it more effective and efficient.

One of the Social Media that currently has many users and is also being discussed is Instagram Social Media. At first, Instagram was only used to post photos which would then reap likes and comments. However, with the rapid development of the internet, the function of the Instagram itself has also become wider. Because of its function that has developed and has many benefits. This is also used by modern marketers to carry out promotions. Social Media Instagram is a digital marketing channel that can be used by companies or business people to carry out promotions. Promotions that can be done through Instagram such as photos or videos that can attract Instagram users. Instagram also has a feature that can help marketing activities, namely Instagram for Business, where companies or marketers can find out or analyze the information they need related to their business. Through this feature, marketers can find out Instagram users who have a tendency or interest in their brand or the promotion they are currently holding.

Tabel 1.1
Media Sosial paling populer di Indonesia, 2020-2021
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Brand awareness according to Hermawan (2014), is the ability of a potential consumer to remember and recognize a brand from a product. The ability of a potential customer to recognize and remember a brand has a big role in his decision. Starbucks is trying to build brand awareness through content posted on its Instagram account which hopes to be able to increase awareness of their brand and survive in pandemic conditions and industry competition. Perceived quality is a total assessment of a product or service that is carried out by consumers by perceiving the expectations they have. One of the best ways to improve the product quality of a brand is with an expectation according to Oliver in Youl Ha (2011). Consumer perceptions of product quality from Starbucks can also be communicated or illustrated through content created by the company on their Instagram account. and later from that content will be able to bring up brand perception of the product. The essence of brand equity is Brand Loyalty according to Aaker (2011). The level of consumer attachment to a brand is called brand loyalty. The possibility of a customer switching to another brand can be described through these levels, especially for brands that have a high element of interest, such as price, for example. Brand loyalty can also be maintained through communication made by the company through its Instagram. This will help maintain loyal consumers so that they can continue to access and find information related to products or promotions more easily. Brand equity or brand equity according to Aaker (2014) are several brand assets and liabilities that are related to a brand, its name and symbol, which increase or decrease the value provided by an item or service to a company or company's customers. Brand Awareness and Brand Loyalty can also affect Brand Equity. Therefore the researcher is interested in discussing the role of Social Media marketing on Brand Equity through Brand Awareness and Brand Loyalty.

Firm-created Content

According to (Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2014) Firm created social media communication is a form of advertising created and controlled by the company and guided by a predetermined marketing strategy agenda. Firm-created social media brand communication defines the communication media that is under the company (Vanden Bergh et al., 2011). Firm-created social media can also be defined as advertisements created by companies that are monitored by marketers. The company's current focus is on developing two-way relationships between customers to increase interaction (Li and Bernoff 2011). Through social media both parties, namely companies and consumers, can also be encouraged to produce more interaction. This social media communication is expected by marketers to be able to deal directly with loyal consumers who can influence consumer perceptions of products, disseminate information, and take lessons from their own consumers (Brodie et al., 2013).

The focus of this Firm-created social media brand communication is Word Of Mouth (WOM) and electronic Word Of Mouth (eWOM) (Balasubramanian and Mahajan. 2001; Chu and Kim, 2011). Not only that, there is an increasing number of Internet users switching from traditional media to social media channels to seek information and opinions about brands and products (Mangold and Faulds 2009; Bambauer-Sachse and Mangold 2011). Even though the types of social media

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communication are increasing nowadays and there are many users, social media channels are still considered as a new way among marketers (Nielsen, 2013).

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is the ability of consumers to recognize and recall a brand that is part of a particular product (Aaker, 2013: 205). According to (Erfan, 2012) states that, one of the elements of brand equity that is often ignored by companies is brand awareness, therefore some brands are not recognized. The ability of consumers to recognize or recall a brand when they search for or think of a product and the brand name can be easily remembered is brand awareness (Shimp, 2014: 97). (Nugroho, 2013) If the brand is easy to remember and is at a vulnerable 17 in consumer recall, this is the most important aspect of brand awareness. Brand awareness refers to the ability of consumers to be able to remember and recognize the brand (Aaker, 2013: 205).

According to (Aaker, 2013: 205) brand awareness measurement based on the level of brand awareness includes top of mind describing the easiest brand to remember and mention about a product, brand recall reflects the next brand association after mentioning the first brand that is remembered, brand recognition where they can remembering and recognizing a brand through the questions given, and brand unaware which is the lowest level in measuring brand awareness, this is a brand that consumers cannot remember or recognize at all regarding a product. Brand awareness is a goal that should be achieved when carrying out marketing communications, it is easy for consumers to recognize and remember a brand, it is expected at any time, the brand will be able to reappear through memory which can then be considered as a final decision or alternative, brand awareness shows consumer knowledge of existence of a brand (Nugroho, 2013). So the level of awareness that consumers have to remember and be aware of the existence of a product is brand awareness.

Perceived Quality

Perceived Quality is how a brand is perceived which includes everything related to the brand so that by knowing the customer's perception of the quality of a brand from a product, the company can determine what steps will be taken to create customer perceptions of the brand owned by the company. the company (Wijaya, et al., 2013). According to (Aaker, 2013: 209), indicators of perceived quality are performance, characteristics, suitability, durability, reliability, service, and end result. Perceived quality is the result of consumer evaluation of a brand, this includes intrinsic elements and extrinsic elements that are owned by the brand, which are intrinsic elements, namely in the form of performance and durability, while those that include extrinsic elements, namely in the form of the brand name of the brand itself (Nor et al. al., 2016). Perceived quality is one of the important roles in building a brand and can be an important reason for purchasing decisions to be made by consumers. (Widiananta and Wardana, 2016) things like good taste, attractive packaging, high quality, various variants, easy to find can be indicators to measure a perception of quality. So perceived quality is the consumer's quality perception of a product or brand through existing indicators. Perceived quality is not the actual quality of the product itself, but is the result of the consumer's evaluation of the product. Perceived quality is the same as brand image, which can be a reason for consumers to make purchasing decisions for a brand that can be distinguished from

its competitors. According to (Fathabadi et al., 2017) consumer perceptions of quality principles are basically related to understanding intrinsic and external qualitative features (Fathabadi et al., 2017).

Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty arises from the perception and love of a brand that he has consumed or used and this can affect consumer interest in the product or brand (Aaker, 2013: 206). Brand loyalty will create a feeling of wanting to repurchase a product from consumers and this has a good impact on consumers, even though consumers often have many alternative product brands that offer better product characteristics (Aaker, 2013: 207). Brand loyalty can show customer loyalty to a particular brand, from that loyalty there will be commitment and high intention to buy it back in the future when the consumer needs it (Listiana, 2015). Loyalty can also be described through consumer behavior where they will show their desire and intention to repurchase in the future the products they have consumed (Bagram and Khan, 2012). (Bagram and Khan, 2012) from a brand there must be something interesting that makes consumers buy products continuously without looking for alternatives or comparing with competing brands.

Loyalty has several levels from the lowest to the highest and each level has a marketing challenge to be faced and is also an asset that can be leveraged. The lowest level of loyalty is switcher (buyers who move around) where consumers do not have a sense of loyalty to a brand, Habitual buyers (buyers who have habits) the habits that are carried out are the fundamental reason for these consumers to make repurchases. Satisfied buyers (buyers who feel satisfied) consumer satisfaction will arise after consumers consume the brand. Even though they are satisfied, there is still a possibility to switch to another brand. Likes the brand (buyers who like the brand) consumers who enter this level are consumers who really like the brand. Committed buyers (buyers who are committed to a particular brand) at this level consumers already have a high level of trust so that a feeling of loyalty to a brand arises. So it can be concluded that brand loyalty is the loyalty that consumers have towards certain brands and makes consumers buy these products continuously.

Brand Equity

According to Aaker (2018: 22) Brand equity is a set of brand assets and liabilities related to a particular brand, its name and logo, which increase or decrease the value provided by a product or service to the company. Some or all of the assets or liabilities can be affected and suffer losses if the name of a brand or logo changes, because assets and liabilities are the basis of brand equity. Brand equity that is built in such a way and is firmly in the minds of customers will make the company have more value and make it stronger than its competitors, besides that companies that have strong brand equity will still be able to compete, seize, and dominate the existing market share. (Sari and Indira, 2017).

Omer, (2014) states that brand equity is also able to provide several advantages such as opportunities and the power of communication. Brand equity is a behavior that is owned by consumers, distribution channel members, and companies that allows a brand to gain strength, durability and excellence that can differentiate it from other brands.

competitor brands (Soebianto, 2014). So brand equity is the added value given to a product so that it can be recognized by consumers.

The relationship between Brand Awareness, Brand Loyalty, Social Media Marketing and Brand Equity

Schivinski and Dabrowski (2015) in Sadek, Elwy, and Eldallal (2017) indicate that social media brand communication helps build positive and unique associations in the minds of consumers. Therefore it is assumed that there is a positive impact from firm-created and user-generated social media communications on brand associations/brand awareness. Hutter et al. (2013) stated that there is a strong relationship between consumer engagement with Facebook pages and brand awareness. Therefore it is assumed that there is a positive influence from social media communication (firm-created and user-generated) on brand awareness.

Firm created social media communication that is reflected simultaneously can be adapted to the concept of branding, a one-way pre-social media channel intended to increase consumer connectedness with brands (Scarth, 2017). It can be concluded that firm created social media communication is a form of advertising that is fully controlled by the company in the form of communication. Social media communication created by companies to create interaction with the community which in the future will lead to consumer perceptions of the company. According to (Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2015) there are 4 measurements used to measure firm created social media communication, namely:

1. Feeling satisfied with firm created social media communication.
2. The level of firm created social media meets expectations.
3. Firm created social media communication is very interesting.
4. Firm created social media communication performs well, when compared to other companies' firm created social media communication

Based on Khalid (2016) in Sadek, Elwy, and Eldallal (2017), firm-created social media communication has a positive influence on brand loyalty. Different from firm-created social media communications, user-generated communications are considered unbiased because other consumers consider the message to be credible and trustworthy (Christodoulides et al., 2012) in Sadek, Elwy, and Eldallal (2017). So, it is assumed that social media communication (firm-created and user-generated) has a positive influence on brand loyalty. According to Durianto, et al (2017: 12) The extent to which a brand has been embedded in the minds of consumers is an important factor in brand awareness, that is that makes the first thing related to brand equity is brand awareness. Consumers will be more inclined to choose and use brands that are already well-known, this is due to consumers' assumptions that a well-known brand is a brand that has good quality (Durianto et al, 2017: 54). Brand awareness and brand equity have a close relationship between the two and brand awareness is a very important component of brand equity, if a product is well known and easily remembered by consumers then this can be an additional value for the brand (Ibrahim 2016).

Brand awareness has several levels from not being aware of the brand (lowest level) to Top of Mind (highest level) (Aaker 2018:91). The following is a sequence of levels or components that affect brand awareness.

1. Not aware of the brand (unware of brand): Consumers here do not have awareness of the existence of a brand and this is the lowest level in the pyramid of brand awareness.
2. Brand recognition (brand recognition): Brand recognition is the second level or minimal level of brand awareness, brand recall, level of brand recognition and recall of a brand through existing assistance. This can be tested through questions related to the brand or through choices given based on a particular product class.
3. Brand recall: Recalling a brand can be asked to mention a particular brand without any assistance related to that brand in a product class, here the respondent does not need to be given assistance related to the brand to remember that brand. Recall without related assistance is a much more difficult task than brand recognition and is associated with a stronger brand position.
4. Top-of-mind awareness: Top-of-mind awareness is a highest position that can be said to be special. This can be defined, the brand becomes the "leader" of various brands that are in the minds of consumers, but that does not mean it cannot be replaced by strong competitors, of course the brand also has strong enough brand rivals that are similar to the brand. .

According to Durianto, et al (2017: 98) the value of a product or service is determined through the perception of the overall quality of a product or service. Consumers' perceived quality of a product can increase brand equity such as consumers who have a positive perception of a brand, so from this perception it can lead to consumer intentions to consume the brand (Ibrahim 2016). According to Muzaqqi, et al (2016) perceived quality cannot be applied objectively, because the impression on quality is perception and also involves important assumptions for consumers. Consumers will be more inclined to choose a quality when choosing a brand. According to Garvin from Harfard (in Aaker 2018: 134) there are seven dimensions of product quality, namely Performance: Covers the main operational matters of a product; Additional parts of the product (features) which are the second part of the product, namely things that become a prominent differentiator between the two products which are almost the same; Compliance with specifications (no product defects) which reduces the presentation of defects from a product and produces products that comply with existing specifications; Reliability, which is the consistency of quality from the previous purchase to the current purchase and the presentation of the time the product has to function as it should, and Durability, which is everything related to the age of a product, how long the product can live and last.

Brand loyalty is the basis of brand equity which can be created from many factors, such as consumer experience in consuming/using. A group of habitual buyers have high scores because they represent a source of profits that are expected to continue to flow over a long time and the attrition rate will be lower for those with stronger levels of loyalty, thereby causing their value get higher. Because of this, it can be said that brand loyalty provides the most important basis for brand equity compared to other dimensions (Aaker 2018: 61). Research conducted by Adiputra (2018) regarding "the effect of brand associations, brand loyalty, brand awareness on brand equity in online private label fashion" from the results of this study proves brand loyalty

has a positive effect on brand equity. This means that the level of brand loyalty will increase or decrease the existing brand equity. Brand loyalty is a bond that exists between consumers and brands where consumers find it difficult to switch to another brand. This is so because it is the result of the trust that consumers place in a brand. Consumers with high loyalty can make repeated purchases over a long period of time. These characteristics include the theory of Schiffman and Kanuk (2004) which explains that the dimensions of brand loyalty consist of four types, namely: Cognitive, Affective, Conative and Action.

Brand Equity has a function as well as benefits that can provide additional value or competitive advantage for a company because people are more likely to buy products that have well-known and respected brand names. According to Duriyanto, et al (2014 in Hesty 2018) brand equity can provide additional value for the company. The following is the value of brand equity for the company: (1). Strong brand equity can help companies to attract potential customers and can increase consumer confidence in the quality of a brand. (2). Strong brand equity can reduce consumers' desire to switch to another brand, so that all dimensions of brand equity can influence consumer purchasing decisions. (3). High loyalty from consumers can minimize or make consumers not switch to competing brands, even though competitors carry out innovations. (4). In evaluating the company's brand expansion strategy decisions, it requires brand associations.

Conclusion

There is a lot of business competition, so the role of social media marketing needs to be strengthened and marketed as attractively as possible in order to get consumers' attention to buy the company's product brands. One of the things companies can do is market their products through Instagram social media. Through Instagram, companies can market their products by posting photos and videos of interesting and unique product brands. Social media is a real form of new media or new media based on advances in communication technology supported by information and communication technology. Social media is understood as a new form of communication on the internet which is supported by various software applications that enable interaction between media users. Social media has several advantages, especially in the ability to interactive two-way communication and makes it easy for users to access various kinds of information without barriers and the distance in which it is very possible for social interaction to occur between individuals and groups, even individuals and groups with masses. Social media marketing really builds brand awareness of a product. Brand awareness is a picture of the existence of a brand in the minds of its consumers which also shows the ability of potential buyers to recognize or recall a brand. Brand awareness is the first step in the purchasing decision process where this awareness will provide an opportunity for the brand to be considered as an alternative product to be purchased.

Several considerations that can be considered in conducting social media marketing so that it has a significant impact are: First, companies can hold different social media marketing programs to increase interest in community participation, such as challenges or give away. Second, companies can organize different social media marketing programs to further increase participant engagement through increasing conversation and community dimensions. Third, the

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concept of social media marketing which is synonymous with brand elements must be maintained, because the concept is different and unique to the brand. As for building brand equity, there are several efforts that can be made. First, use social media other than Instagram to carry out social media marketing so as to increase online traffic in various places. Second, create a social media marketing concept that is closely related to brand elements so that it has strength and is different from competitors because the brand association index value occupies the highest position. Third, people can use social media marketing to be able to create a presence in cyberspace so as to increase brand awareness because the brand awareness index value obtained in this study occupies the second highest position. Fourth, Social media marketing can be used to strengthen communities around brands that are formed offline.

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